

FEATURES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF BUSINESS MODELS AT CHEMICAL INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *The article describes the structure, classification, features of management models at chemical industry enterprises, organization and stages of managerial work. The importance of improving management models is described.*

Keywords: *industrial enterprises, chemical industry, management model, management system, distribution of powers, stages, process description.*

The dynamics of the modern business environment involves the constant emergence of new technologies, changing consumer preferences, the emergence of social trends, the formation of new political and economic conditions for entrepreneurial activity. These processes are taking place before everyone's eyes, but the profound changes in the technological and socio-economic patterns to which they lead force enterprises to constantly look for new, more sustainable formats for organizing the management system. In such conditions, the main success factor of the company is the development of a management model that is fully compatible with the factors and trends of the external environment. In other words, the choice of the optimal management model for the existing external situation, on the one hand, presupposes the success of the enterprise, and on the other hand, determines the level of its viability.

The process of creating an enterprise management model is very dynamic and complex. Today, a modern enterprise is an open socio-technical system, and the main sources of success are the factors of the internal and external environment. In this regard, the presence of a clear idea of the company's development prospects using systematic approaches of strategic and situational management is the main factor in the company's competitiveness.

In a general sense, the development of a management model is a special cyclic sequence of interrelated stages leading to the organization of the enterprise. In this process, the main function of planning is the process of designing the main goal of the enterprise and effective ways to achieve it. The end result of this process is planned decisions that serve as the basis for the purposeful activities of the enterprise.

In the conditions of modern market relations, an enterprise operates in conditions of high instability of the external environment, which always leads to an increase in the level of uncertainty in making managerial decisions and an increase in economic risks in the process of achieving goals. The strategic interests of modern enterprises are to adapt to the influence of the external environment and ensure sustainable development. The more accurate the dynamics of environmental factors and the higher the uncertainty, the more important the problem of developing and implementing a management model becomes.

Modern management models are developed on the basis of digital technologies. Small-cap digital technology platforms are emerging across all industries, becoming service providers and e-commerce businesses for customers. They have a number of advantages over traditional enterprises:

- Orientation to the client;

- Flexibility and efficiency;
- Economic efficiency of business models.
- Integration of the value chain between producer and buyer.

In response, traditional businesses across industries are seizing opportunities to expand their business management models beyond their core competencies, achieving high rates of change, customer recognition, and better financial results, ensuring the viability of their business [1].

Thus, the management model is understood as the organization of the main financial, structural, personnel, technological and marketing activities of the enterprise, its structural elements, their relationships, as well as the principles that determine the effectiveness of the enterprise.

Figure 1.4. Management model for chemical industry enterprises [2]

The management model consists of various business components, including entrepreneurship, effective competitive strategy, marketing strategy, economic strategy, and sustainable growth strategies. Also, the management model turns innovative projects into economic value, clearly defines their place in the value chain of the enterprise and sets the direction for achieving economic efficiency.

In industrial enterprises, the management model includes the creation of value, its distribution, as well as the receipt of income through the influence of suppliers and consumers. The value chain is based on the supply-demand-distribution-exchange-consumption-demand scheme.

Businesses and organizations are forced to constantly adapt and change their management models in response to market changes. As a rule, each development strategy has its own model, that is, models change every 3-5 years. In recent decades, technological changes have become the main factor in the external environment, which is beginning to change management models.

Develop a strategy for promoting products or services on the site. The SMM manager must determine the target audience, determine the needs and interests of the audience. Also, the manager is required to improve the usability of the site in order to maintain loyalty to the site.

Increasing the competitiveness of the enterprise through advertising. The manager must predict the costs associated with advertising on the network, and its results.

Control of the company's reputation on the Internet. The manager must monitor public opinion online and deal with complaints and objections to products or services.

Development and placement of high-quality content on the network. When preparing articles, posts, videos about enterprises, it is necessary to convey materials to the majority of the audience.

Ability to analyze the activities of competing enterprises. It is required to be able to apply the best practices in your own way after studying the activities of industrial enterprises.

In general, when developing management models for industrial enterprises, it is important to analyze the activities of competing enterprises, study the most advanced methods of entering the market, establish the activities of SMM managers, and improve the system for creating additional value.

The role of SMM (Social Media Marketing) managers in the field of social media marketing is important in improving the management models of industrial enterprises. SMM managers need to be familiar with the social media environment, to be able to work with a specific audience.

As the main functions, SMM managers are offered:

It is known that the chemical industry is one of the basic sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan, and based on the need to accelerate the production of agricultural products, enterprises for the production of mineral fertilizers were created.

At present JSC Maksam-Chirchik, Navoiyazot and Fergonazot produce nitrogen fertilizers, ammonium nitrate, carbamide, ammonium sulfate. The joint-stock companies "Ammophos", "Samarkankimyo" and "Kokon superphosphate plant" produce phosphate fertilizers ammophos, suprefos, simple ammonium superphosphate, ammonium sulfophosphate and nitrocalcium phosphate. The raw materials for them are supplied by the Kyzylkum Phosphorite Plant. JV "Elektrokhimzavod" produces chemical means of plant protection.

Over the past five years, 16 investment projects worth \$2 billion 100 million have been implemented in the chemical industry, and 3,000 new jobs have been created. Another important aspect is that the private sector has entered the industry and launched 8 projects worth \$45 million.

Over these five years, production in the chemical industry has increased 1.5 times, the volume of exports has increased from \$190 million to \$310 million. It is expected that by the end of this year, the total net profit of enterprises will increase by more than 8 times and exceed 1 trillion soums.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 13, 2021, it is planned to create 4 more technological chemical clusters aimed at the production of high-quality goods in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Tashkent, Navoi and Fergana

regions. They produce more than 20 kinds of products, such as carbon fiber, polyester fiber, acetate fiber, polyvinyl acetate, potassium nitrate. [3].

Along with advances in the chemical industry, there are some challenges in the industry:

- chemical products that can be manufactured and do not have a complex composition are still imported;

- 60 percent of the used equipment is morally and physically worn out, and fixed assets consume energy 2-3 times more than the norm;

- the production system has not been developed in accordance with international standards for improving product quality;

- low level of automation of processes dangerous for human life, digitalization of industrial enterprises;

- the work to increase the investment attractiveness of enterprises and the wide attraction of foreign investors is not organized at the proper level.

In addressing the above issues, each industrial enterprise needs to develop a clear strategy. The management system plays an important role in the implementation of the developed strategy, economic efficiency and competitive advantages.

It is known that the application of the concept of management to the industrial enterprises of the world has become widespread in a short time. New management models have begun to be created for companies operating in different markets. In parallel, scientists conducted research on management models.

Research in recent years points to three main innovative types of management models:

- industrial-level innovations, that is, significant changes in the vertical value chain, leading to a completely new and radical reform of existing industries, as well as the development of unique assets and competencies;

- when the role of an enterprise in the value chain of an industry changes due to innovation at the enterprise level, that is, enterprise restructuring or the creation of a networked integrated structure of a business organization, these processes often change the configuration of assets, capacities and dynamic capabilities;

- innovation at the level of consumer supply, that is, the introduction of innovation at the level of consumer supply by increasing the cost of products and improving the quality of services, as well as introducing a new pricing model.

By types of products, enterprises can be divided into the following production complexes:

- complex for the production of mineral fertilizers, inorganic substances and chemical reagents for energy, gold mining and chemical industries;

- complex for the production of organic chemistry, artificial fibers and polymeric materials;

- complex for the production of chemical plant protection products;

- complex for the production of soda ash.

Enterprises of JSC "Uzkimiyosanoat" produce more than 170 types of chemical products [4].

The foundation created in the industry in recent years can ensure the potential of the chemical industry with stable growth dynamics for the next 3-5 years. However, in order to create a solid foundation for the long-term sustainable development of all areas of the chemical industry, it is necessary to accelerate the transformation of the industry based on the most advanced foreign

experience [5]. The management system of chemical industry enterprises needs to be improved in order to ensure the fulfillment of the tasks set by the head of state.

The chemical industry, like other industries, in developing an effective management system should conduct a thorough study of existing markets, while:

- employees of the enterprise, their composition, skill level, dissatisfaction, motivational training and organization of a system for working with reserve personnel;
- production capacity, capabilities, compliance with existing demand;
- the financial potential of the enterprise, the level of financial independence;
- the possibility of attracting loans for financing;
- takes into account the possibility of implementing innovative projects in the market in order to increase its capabilities.

In general, as a result of the application of a modern management system at the enterprises of the chemical industry, the following is achieved:

- an industrial enterprise establishes a management system based on a clear strategic focus;
- all managers and employees are managed on the basis of functional tasks, a vertical management system;
- increase the market value of the enterprise, manage the brand strategy, investment attractiveness is achieved;
- innovations will be introduced at operating enterprises of the chemical industry based on the model, a clear mission will be developed to fight for competitive advantage;
- the factors of the external and internal environment of enterprises are analyzed analytically, specific measures are developed to prevent business losses.

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